

Extractive spectrophotometric study of adsorption and leaching of malathion on four Indian soils

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Abstract : Pesticide adsorption by soil affects its toxicity, mobility, persistence and volatilization which in turn influence the ground water contamination through leaching. The leaching potential of the pesticide is evaluated in terms of ground water ubiquity score. An extractive spectrophotometric study of the adsorption of malathion on four soils of different soil characteristics has been carried out with a view to evaluate its leaching potential. The proposed study is based on the microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of the insecticide to dimethyl dithiophosphate which form yellow coloured chloroform extractable complex with copper(II) acetate showing maximum absorbance at 419 nm. The ground water ubiquity score (GUS) of malathion with all the soil types has been found in the range 1.38–1.60, which classify it as a non leacher insecticide and hence it does not represent hazard to ground water contamination.

Keywords : Malathion, extractive spectrophotometric study, soil adsorption, leaching.

Introduction

The environmental fate of pesticides is strongly influenced by their interaction with soil as the latter is the ultimate reservoir for these chemicals irrespective of their application target. Pesticide adsorption by the soil is a naturally occurring phenomenon which affects the various processes like toxicity, mobility, persistence and volatilization which in turn affect ground and surface water contamination¹. The frequent detection of pesticides in surface water and groundwater has led to a number of experimental studies on adsorption of malathion and related insecticides for evaluation of their leaching potential²⁻⁸. Hence, thorough understanding of pesticide adsorption on soil is of great importance for the prediction of its movement in soils and water bodies. In continuation to our earlier work on the adsorption study of thiophanate methyl on some soils⁹, the present study dealing with the adsorption of malathion on some soils has been undertaken.

Malathion is a nonsystemic organophosphorous insecticide widely used to control insects that attack fruits, vegetables, cereals and stored grains^{10,11}. Like other pesticides, malathion is also toxic and its adverse effects on human health and ecosystem are also reported in

literature¹⁰⁻¹⁴. In the present work an extractive spectrophotometric study of the adsorption of malathion on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics has been carried out. Though malathion has been determined by various analytical methods¹⁵⁻²², spectrophotometric methods being simple and easily accessible in all laboratories are extensively used. The spectrophotometric study is based on colour reaction of dimethyl dithiophosphate (formed from microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of the malathion) with copper(II) acetate forming chloroform extractable yellow product showing maximum absorbance at 419 nm. The various adsorption parameters viz. soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}) and Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) and Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) for predicting leaching behaviour of the insecticide in terms of groundwater contamination has been calculated.

Results and discussion

Concern about the environmental impact of excessive use of malathion insecticide has prompted research into the environmental fate of this insecticide²⁻⁴. The behaviour of malathion in soil is strongly influenced by soil characteristics which is an important consideration for the evalu-

ation of its environmental toxicity in terms of surface and groundwater contamination. The proposed spectrophotometric study of the adsorption and leaching of malathion is based on the colour reaction of DMDTP (hydrolytic product of the microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of the malathion), with copper(II) acetate in 2 : 1 molar ratio to form chloroform extractable yellow complex (I) showing maximum absorbance (λ_{\max}) at 419 nm (Fig. 1).

lar absorptivity (ϵ) and Sandell's sensitivity (S) values of $2.084 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.1585 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The linear regression equation has the value of slope and intercept as 0.00641 and 0.0047 respectively with a correlation coefficient 0.998. Malathion in the range 11.0–88.0 μg have been determined with a maximum relative standard deviation (RSD) of 0.87%. To assess the validity of the proposed method in soil adsorption

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of $\text{Cu}(\text{DMDTP})_2$ complex.

The microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis has been demonstrated to be reproducible, time saving and effective technique^{23,24}. The effect of time of hydrolysis and extracting solvent on the development, stability and sensitivity of the colour were studied and best results have been obtained corresponding to 40 s hydrolysis time in the microwave and chloroform for extracting the coloured product. The kinetic stability of the yellow product under optimised condition has been found to be 120 min. Under the optimised condition the Beer's law is obeyed in the range 5.5–110.1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of malathion (Fig. 2) with mo-

Fig. 2. Relationship between absorbance and concentration (calibration graph) for malathion.

study, the effect of common ions present in soil was studied in determination of insecticide. The method has been found to be free from interferences of most of common ions viz. Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , PO_4^{3-} , CH_3COO^- .

The adsorption isotherms of malathion on four soils of different soil characteristics (Table 1) have been evaluated by Freundlich's adsorption eq. (1)

$$X = K_f C_e^{nf} \quad (1)$$

Fig 3. Adsorption isotherms of malathion on four different soils (error bars represent the standard deviations of three replicates).

Table 1. Characteristics of the different Indian soils used in the adsorption study of malathion

Soil sample	pH	Clay (%)	Organic carbon (%)	Cation Exchange Capacity (meq/100 g)
I	7.2	32.6	0.8	13.1
II	7.6	18.2	0.9	12.9
III	6.5	20.0	1.5	11.0
IV	6.8	23.4	1.6	12.8

where X is the amount of pesticide adsorbed mg kg^{-1} of the adsorbent; C_e is the equilibrium concentration in solution (mg L^{-1}). Three equations are generally used to study the adsorption phenomena : Langmuir equation, Freundlich equation and Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation. Several studies on adsorption of pesticides in soils show that Freundlich isotherm is most reliable because of possible rigorous derivation and more realistic assumptions compared with other equations^{3,25}. Based on the Giles classification the isotherms obtained for malathion are of L-type²⁶⁻²⁸ (Fig. 3). This type of iso-

therms indicates that there is a relatively high affinity between the soil and insecticide. K_f is the Freundlich's adsorption coefficient and n_f is a dimensionless parameter that accounts for nonlinearity of an isotherm. These coefficients have been calculated from the plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ (Fig. 4) by using the linear form of the Freundlich's adsorption eq. (2).

$$\log X = \log K_f + n_f \log C_e \tag{2}$$

The value of n_f observed with all soil types is less than one is indicative of the fact that there is minimum competition from solvent molecules for adsorption sites on the adsorbing surface²⁹⁻³¹. The adsorption coefficient K_f represents the amount of pesticide adsorbed at an equilibrium concentration of 1 mg L^{-1} and higher the value of K_f , the lower is the tendency of pesticide to move in soil. The other adsorption parameters viz. soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}), Gibb's free energy (ΔG^0) and Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) have been calculated by using eqs. (3)–(6) respectively^{3,32,33}.

$$K_d = \frac{X}{C_e} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_d \quad (4)$$

$$K_{oc} = K_d \times \left(\frac{100}{\%OC} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$GUS = \log t_{1/2} [4 - \log (K_{oc})] \quad (6)$$

where R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature, $t_{1/2}$ = pesticide persistence (half life), OC = organic carbon content of soil. The adsorption parameters for malathion on all soil types are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ for the evaluation of Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f for malathion.

Table 2. Adsorption parameters of malathion on four different soils at 25 ± 1 °C

Soil	k_f	n_f	K_d	K_{oc}	$\log K_{oc}$	ΔG°	GUS
I	11.36	0.68	3.78	472	2.67	-3.296	1.38
II	10.64	0.69	3.64	404	2.60	-3.201	1.45
III	15.12	0.64	4.49	299	2.47	-3.725	1.58
IV	14.99	0.65	4.56	285	2.45	-3.761	1.60

The value of K_d represents the extent of adsorption and in general higher the value of K_d greater is the adsorption of the pesticide²⁹. The K_d values for malathion have been found in the range 3.64 to 4.56 L/kg (Table 2) indicating that the adsorption of malathion increased with increasing organic carbon content in all the four soils as they provide soils with an increased number of adsorptive sites onto which the pesticides molecules can bind.

That this is so has also been reported in the literature². The organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}) which is less soil specific is calculated by normalizing adsorption coefficient (K_d) with the organic carbon (OC) content of the soil³⁴. Higher K_{oc} value (greater than 1000) indicates that pesticide is very strongly adsorbed and is immobile in soil; values ≤ 100 infer weak adsorption and tend to move with water and have the potential to leach or move with run off water³⁵. The observed values of K_{oc} in the range 285–472 (Table 2) suggest that malathion is moderately adsorbed on to soils. The pH is another important factor governing the adsorption of pesticides. In general the adsorption of pesticides is less in alkaline than in acidic soils³⁶. However, at quite higher and lower pH of the soil, the adsorption of pesticides decreases due to change in the clay mineralogy or destroying of the crystal lattice³⁷. In the present case similar trend has also been observed i.e. the adsorption of malathion increases with increase in pH of the soil upto 7 and then decreases on further rise in pH. Similar behaviour has also been reported by Bhardwaj, Sharma and Tomar³. The value of CEC of soil also affects to some extent the adsorption of pesticides. In general the value of CEC of soil is the measure of hydrophobicity of its surface. Malathion being hydrophobic organic pesticide with low water solubility also shows significant adsorption in soils. The negative values of Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) for the adsorption suggest that the adsorption is spontaneous and energetically favourable process. Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) is used for predicting the leaching behaviour of pesticides. Generally they can be classified as leacher ($GUS > 2.8$), transition ($2.8 > GUS < 1.8$) and non-leacher ($GUS < 1.8$)³⁸. It is determined by using experimentally observed K_{oc} value for each soil sample and literature reported half life³³ of malathion. The leaching potential of malathion in terms of Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) has been found below 1.80, which classify it as a nonleacher insecticide.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Spectronic 20D⁺ spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells. Domestic microwave (Samsung make) was used for microwave assisted hydrolysis experiments. In-

cubator Shaker PT-422, manufactured by Popular Traders, Ambala Cantt. was used for equilibration study of the pesticide during soil adsorption studies.

Reagents and samples :

Acetonitrile (Merck) was kept over phosphorus pentoxide (5 g L^{-1}) and distilled twice. The analytical standard of malathion (PolyScience, USA) was used and its stock solution (10^{-3} M) was prepared in acetonitrile. Copper(II) acetate monohydrate (CDH, AR) which exist in dimeric form $\text{Cu}_2(\text{OAc})_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was used. Its $\approx 0.01 \text{ M}$ solution in water was prepared by dissolving 0.2 g of copper(II) acetate monohydrate in distilled water and diluting to 100 mL with the same solvent. Chloroform (Merck, GR) was used as received. The four soils samples used in the adsorption study were collected from different regions of Solan District of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Preparation of calibration graph for pure compound :

Aliquots (0.1–2.5 mL) of standard solution of malathion (10^{-3} M in acetonitrile) were taken in 10 mL-measuring flasks and volume made to 2.5 mL with acetonitrile. Each solution was mixed with 1 mL of 0.2 M aqueous potassium hydroxide and diluted to 5 mL with water and kept in microwave for 40 s. Each hydrolyzed malathion solution was then treated with 4 mL of 0.2 M aqueous acetic acid not only to neutralize the excess alkali but also to make the condition acidic. Finally 1 mL, 0.01 M aqueous copper(II) acetate was added to each solution. Each mixture solution was transferred to 100 mL-separating funnel and equilibrated with 4 mL of chloroform for 5 min. The intense yellow coloured chloroform layer was separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) and its volume made to 6 mL with chloroform. The absorbance of yellow chloroform extract was measured at 419 nm, the wavelength of maximum absorbance of solution (Fig. 1) against reagent blank and a calibration graph was prepared (Fig. 2).

Soil adsorption study :

Malathion adsorption isotherms on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics (Table 1) were obtained by the batch equilibration technique using 50 mL conical flasks. Triplicate soil samples (2 g) were equilibrated with malathion solutions in the concentration range from 33.03–99.10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ by shaking in Incubator Shaker at room temperature ($25 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for 24 h equilibrium time. After

equilibration, the suspensions were centrifuged and 5 mL of supernatant was taken and the equilibrium concentrations (C_e) were determined by the method described above.

Conclusion

The pesticide leaching is an important process with respect to contamination risk to aquatic environment which has been evaluated in terms of GUS by using experimentally observed K_{oc} values for each soil type and literature reported half life of the insecticide. The observed K_{oc} values in the range 285–472 suggest moderate adsorption of malathion in all four soil types which is in consistent with the reported data in that K_{oc} values greater than 1000 infer very strong adsorption and values less than 100 corresponds to weak adsorption. Consequently GUS values have been observed in the range 1.38–1.60 classifying malathion as non-leacher. Though the insecticide does not represent hazards to surface and groundwater contamination but its toxicity can be reduced by adjusting its application dose according to soil properties. Further soils with high organic carbon content can increase its adsorption and consequently reduce the leaching losses. Hence, it is advisable that organic amendments such as farmyard manure and compost will help not only in this regard but also improve the soil fertility and health by serving as source of soil nutrients. Further, the proposed extractive spectrophotometric study of adsorption and leaching of malathion is simple, sensitive and free from interferences of common ions present in soil and hence is of wide applicability.

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